

DEVELOPMENT OF THE GRAPHITE EPOXY SATELLITE STRUCTURE

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Summary

The development work carried out on the application of graphite epoxy composite material to the primary structure of future high power geosynchronous communications satellite (550 kg class on-orbit) to be launched by H-1 launch vehicle is described. The development includes design, analysis, fabrication and tests of the satellite primary structure and its structural elements.

Design studies have shown that structure mass can be reduced significantly by using graphite-epoxy composites and 59 kg weight satellite structure can be achieved. Two full-scale center cylinders and thrust cones which are primary load path for the satellite have been fabricated and successfully tested to ultimate compression static loads. A full-scale satellite structure assembly has been fabricated and subjected to static load test and modal survey test. The test results have shown that the structure meet both strength and stiffness requirements of H-1 launch vehicle interface.

Introduction

New launch vehicles have been developed as large satellites need to be launched in Japan. Now, H-1 launch vehicle which can launch 550 kg (on orbit) class satellite on geosynchronous orbit is under development and the first flight is scheduled in 1985. Among the satellites launched by H-1 launch vehicle, a high power communications satellite such as broadcasting satellite requires a structure as light as possible since reducing the structure mass increase the communication payload and propellant which bring the improvement of service. The application of advanced composites to satellite primary structure was considered for the structure mass reduction due to the inherently higher stiffness-to-weight ratio of the materials. The development work of design, analysis, fabrication, and testing of a graphite-epoxy satellite structure was started and have been successfully performed.

The typical high power communications satellite to investigate for the structure mass reduction is shown in Figure 1. The satellite is the three-axis stabilized satellite with sun-oriented solar panels and an earth-oriented fixed antenna. The weight of the satellite is 1080 kg at separation and 580 kg on orbit (BOL). Less than 65 kg was decided as a design goal for the structure weight from consideration of system weight allocation.

Figure 1 SATELLITE CONFIGURATION

Design Configuration

Configuration and Components

The primary structure, shown in Figure 2, consists of the following three major assemblies.

- i) Center Body
- ii) Equipment Panels
- iii) Secondary Propulsion Subsystem (SPS) Support Structure

The Center Body consists of a center cylinder/thrust cone, three deck panels, shear webs, and east/west side panels. These components are permanently assembled by bonding.

The Equipment Panels are removable from the Center Body and consist of two mission equipment panels and two service equipment panels. The SPS Support Structure consists of east/west side panels and support truss for each of the two propellant tanks, and other SPS module support structures. The SPS, complete with SPS modules and these supporting structure, can be assembled as a module with the aid of the assembly fixture which maintains the relative position of the components until the assembly is matched with the Center Body.

Figure 2 SATELLITE STRUCTURE CONSTRUCTION

Materials and Constructions

Material tradeoffs conducted on various metals and advance composite materials selected graphite epoxy composite or carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CRRP) as prime material. Beryllium is the most attractive material due to its high stiffness and good thermal conductivity but rejected for a number of reasons - brittleness, high toxicity in machining, long delivery time, high cost etc. High-modulus unidirectional prepreg sheets (Toray M40 type) are used for the most of graphite epoxy laminates and high-strength unidirectional prepreg (Toray T300 type) or woven cloths are used partially.

Structural tradeoffs were performed and graphite epoxy face sheet sandwich construction was selected for the most part of the structure due to its high stiffness-to-weight ratio. Table I presents major construction material, and size of the structure components. The center cylinder/thrust cone is the most highly loaded structure transferring most of satellite loads and designed primarily on the basis of axial compressive loads and bending moments. The primary failure mode involves shell buckling. The graphite epoxy facesheet sandwich design result in lighter structure compared monocoque or semi-monocoque shell design. However, the AKM ring which supports the apogee kick motor (AKM), and the adapter ring which mate with the launch vehicle adapter are of aluminum alloy (7075) since high strength to local stress and machining accuracy are required. The sandwich construction is selected for the equipment panel due to its high stiffness-to-weight ratio but the material for face sheet is aluminum since good thermal and electrical conductivity is required for the panel.

Table I STRUCTURE CONSTRUCTION, MATERIAL AND SIZE

COMPONENT		CONSTRUCTION	MATERIALS/SIZE
CENTER BODY	CENTER CYLINDER /THRUST CONE	HONEYCOMB SANDWICH CYLINDER, CONE AND MACHINED RINGS (ADAPTER, AKM) ASSEMBLY	GR/EP FACESHEET/ALUM HONEYCOMB CORE - CYLINDER 5mm THICK, CONE 7mm THICK MACHINED ALUM 7075 FORGED RING
	DECK PANELS (UPPER,MIDDLE • LOWER)	HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANEL	GR/EP FACESHEET/ALUM HONEYCOMB CORE 15mm THICK (UPPER), 6.7mm THICK (MIDDLE, LOWER)
	SHEAR WEBS, EAST/WEST PANELS etc.	HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANELS AND SHAPED LAMINATES	GR/EP FACESHEET/ALUM HONEYCOMB CORE AND GR/EP SHAPED LAMINATES
EQUIPMENT PANEL	NORTH MISSION EQUIPMENT PANEL	HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANEL (HEAT PIPES ASSEMBLED)	ALUM FACESHEET/ALUM HONEYCOMB CORE 15.7mm THICK
	SOUTH MISSION EQUIPMENT PANEL		
	SOUTH SERVICE EQUIPMENT PANEL	HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANEL	ALUM FACESHEET/ALUM HONEYCOMB CORE 15.7mm THICK
	SOUTH SERVICE EQUIPMENT PANEL		
SECONDARY PROPULSION SUB-SYSTEM (SPS) SUPPORT STRUCTURE	HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANEL AND ASSEMBLED STRUT	GR/EP FACESHEET/ALUM HONEYCOMB CORE 16mm THICK GR/EP TUBE AND MACHINED ALUM FITTING	

Weight

The weight of the primary structure mostly calculated from the drawings is 59 kg which satisfies the design goal (less than 65 kg) and equal to 5.5 percent of the satellite weight at separation and 10 percent of the initial satellite weight in geosynchronous orbit. The weight breakdown within structure components is shown in Table II.

Table II STRUCTURE WEIGHT BREAKDOWN

COMPONENT	WEIGHT (kg)
CENTER BODY	35.5
EQUIPMENT PANEL	17.0
SPS SUPPORT STRUCTURE	4.3
FASTENERS	2.2
SUM	59.0

Analysis

The primary structure has been structurally sized mainly by the quasi-static launch vehicle accelerations and stiffness criteria from interface requirements with the H-1 launch vehicle. The structural dynamic analysis, and stress analysis has been performed and the structure design meets the requirements has been confirmed.

Dynamic Analysis

Finite element stiffness and mass models made from stress analysis model by static reduction were used for frequency and mode shape calculations.

The analysis results of the satellite fundamental frequencies for the satellite hard-mounted at the launcher/satellite separation plane are listed in Table III compared with requirements. Figure 3 represents the first satellite lateral-Y axis mode.

Table III SATELLITE FUNDAMENTAL FREQUENCY

MODE 2 FREQ. 19.778 HZ

AXIS	REQUIREMENT	ANALYSIS RESULTS
(X) TRANSVERSE (Y)	15 Hz (MIN)	19.5 Hz
		19.8 Hz
THRUST (Z)	35 Hz (MIN)	53.2 Hz

Figure 3 FIRST SATELLITE LATERAL-Y AXIS MODE

Stress Analysis

Strength requirements are the structure shall withstand the limit load without permanent deformation more than 0.2 percent and withstand the ultimate load without failure by rupture or instability. The limit load (design) is shown in Table IV and the ultimate load is defined as the limit load multiplied by 1.25. Analysis results have shown that the margin of safety (M.S) of all the components are greater than zero. Figure 4 presents the values and positions of minimum margin of safety for each structural components under the limit or ultimate design loads. Stress analysis at sub-structure level also has been performed under design loads derived from the vibration environment and confirmed that the structure has sufficient strength.

Table IV Limit Design Loads

Load Case	Acceleration Load (G)		
	X	Y	Z
Lift-off (XZ)	3.0	/	-3.6
Lift-off (YZ)	/	3.0	-3.6
POGO/MECO (XZ)	1.5	/	-14.7
POGO/MECO (YZ)	/	1.5	-14.7

Figure 4 MINIMUM MARGIN OF SAFETY

Fabrication and Tests

Fabrication and Testing Flow

Fabrication and testing of the structural elements and full-scale model have been performed to establish the manufacturing method and verify the design. Figure 5 presents the fabrication and testing flow. The coupon/structural elements fabrication and tests were performed at program start to establish design parameters and manufacturing process. Two full-scale center cylinders and thrust cones which are main structure components and primary load path for the satellite have been fabricated and tested prior to the full-scale complete structure model fabrication. Static load test and modal survey test with the full-scale structure model have been conducted to evaluate structure strength and dynamic characteristic respectively:

Figure 5 FABRICATION AND TESTING FLOW

Fabrication

The conical and cylindrical sandwich shells formed separately are bonded on the AKM and Adapter rings and the center cylinder/thrust cone assembly is completed. Figure 6 presents a photograph of the assembly. The center body is completed by bonding pre-formed deck panels, shear webs, east/west panels on the center cylinder/thrust cone assembly. The removable equipment panels and SPS support structure are installed on the center body with fasteners and the satellite structure (main body) is completed. Figure 7 presents a photograph of the satellite structure with the equipment panels removed.

The weight of the structure model designed to be subjected to the static load and vibration tests is lighter than the prime hardware (flight model) design since some parts like inserts and secondary structure like brackets are not incorporated. The actual weight of the fabricated model is 54 kg which nearly equal to the calculated weight based on the drawings.

Figure 6 CENTER CYLINDER/THRUST CONE ASSEMBLY

Figure 7 SATELLITE STRUCTURE

Coupon/Structural Elements Tests

Various kinds of specimens have been tested to obtain design parameters for the laminated plates and structural elements. Especially, structural elements tests put emphasis on the bonded joint elements and the shear panels (webs) of the center body. Figure 8 presents a photograph of the test setup of the shear panel with hole. The test results agreed well with the analysis results.

Center Cylinder/Thrust Cone Static Load Test

Two full-scale center cylinders and two full-scale thrust cones were subjected to compression loads test. The compression load is applied by an actuator (hydraulic jack). Design loads for each cylinder and cone have been determined as shown in Table V based on the satellite structural analysis results.

Test results are summarized as follows.

- o Both cylinder and cone withstood the design limit and ultimate loads without failure.
- o Residual strains present after unloading from limit loads are negligible small. (less than 0.003%)
- o Strain and displacement data agreed well with analysis results. Figure 9 presents load-displacement curve at the top of thrust cone as an example.
- o Failure load for the cylinder agreed well with predicted value by analysis as shown in Table VI. Figure 10 presents a photograph of the cylinder at the state of failure.

Figure 8 SHEAR PANEL TEST

Table VI Design Loads (Compression)
(ton)

	Limit load	Ultimate load
Center cylinder	8	10
Thrust cone	16	20

Table VII Center Cylinder Failure Load
(ton)

Analysis	Test Results		
	#1	#2	Av.
20	19	17	18

Figure 9 LOAD-DISPLACEMENT (TOP OF CONE)

Figure 10 CYLINDER STATIC LOAD TEST

Satellite Structure Static Load Test

A full-scale structure model has been subjected to static load test to simulate the effect of critical launch events. MECO/POGO load conditions have been selected as most critical test conditions. Testing has been performed to the qualification test level loads in 20 percent increments and returned to zero by unloading. Loads have been applied with a wiffle tree arrangement as illustrated in Figure 11. Strains and displacements of structure are measured by strain gauge and dial gauge respectively. Figure 12 presents a photo of test set up.

The results are summarized as follows.

- o Structure withstood the qualification test level loads (equal to design limit loads) without failure.
- o Residual strains present after unloading are very small - less than 0.014%.
- o Strain and displacement data show a good agreement with analysis results.

POGO XZ

POGO YZ

Figure 12 STATIC LOAD TEST SET UP

Figure 11 STATIC LOAD TEST CONFIGURATION

Modal Survey Test

Test specimen consists of the structure model subjected to static load test, mass simulated dummies of components and an antenna. The weight of test specimen is approximately 1 ton equal to the total weight of the satellite. Figure 13 presents the test specimen.

The test specimen mounted on the vibration fixture have been excited along the three axis (X, Y and Z). Response acceleration are measured by accelerometers installed on the test specimen and the fixture. Figure 14 presents the photograph of Y-axis test setup.

Low level random and low level sinusoidal sweep tests have been conducted.

Test results have shown that the structure model meet the stiffness requirements and the validity of dynamic analytical models are confirmed. Table VIII presents the test results of the satellite fundamental frequencies compared with analysis results of test configuration.

Figure 15 presents the first satellite lateral-X axis mode derived from the test results.

Figure 13 TEST SPECIMEN

Figure 14 Y-AXIS TEST SET-UP

Table VIII SATELLITE FUNDAMENTAL FREQUENCY

	Test	Analysis	Δf	
Transverse	(X)	19.6 Hz	20.4Hz	3.9 %
	(Y)	20.5 Hz	20.8 Hz	1.4 %
Thrust	Z	69.0 Hz	66.7 Hz	3.4 %

NOTE:
$$\Delta f = \frac{\text{TEST}(f) - \text{ANALYSIS}(f)}{\text{ANALYSIS}(f)} \times 100$$

MODE 1 FREQ. 19.630 HZ

Figure 15 FIRST X-AXIS MODE

Conclusions

Conclusions derived from the development work of the graphite epoxy structure are as follows:

- . It has been confirmed by design, analysis, fabrication and tests that a light-weight satellite structure can be achieved by using graphite epoxy composite construction.
- . The design and analysis techniques on the application of graphite epoxy composite have been verified by component and system level structural tests.
- . Manufacturing method and process for the graphite epoxy application, based on the existing technology have been established through the success of fabrication and tests.